

Investment Recommendation System using Reinforcement learning: A Survey

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Abstract - Investor choice is regularly hampered by behavioral biases including loss aversion, impulsiveness, and overconfidence, which are not catered to by conventional portfolio optimization models because of their rationality assumptions. With developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), it now becomes feasible to systematically identify and curb these biases so that more adaptive and tailored investment plans can be made. This paper surveys recent studies on AI technology in behavioral finance and suggests a multi-layered system architecture incorporating behavioral profiling, market data analysis, explainable AI, and continuous learning mechanisms. The proposed framework bridges available gaps in dynamic behavioral modeling and transparency and serves as a basis for intelligent, user-oriented financial advisory systems

Key Words: Behavioral Finance, Investor Biases, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Explainable AI, Portfolio Optimization, Adaptive Systems

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial markets are conventionally described in the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) framework, where it is assumed that investors are rational maximizers of utility. Behavioral finance refutes this postulate by showing that investors systematically depart from rationality because of cognitive and affective biases. Prospect Theory researches by Kahneman and Tversky (1979) cemented that people are disproportionately loss-averse relative to equivalent gains a phenomenon seen as loss aversion.

As digital trading platforms have become more prominent, retail investors create enormous volumes of transactional and behavioral data. Such data offer a chance to study impulsiveness, overconfidence, and herding patterns. At the same time, the financial sector is progressively embracing artificial intelligence for prediction, portfolio management, and risk evaluation. The problem lies in combining behavioral modeling with AI-based decision-making. The majority of AI investment systems maximize returns against market signals, not taking into consideration the behavioral aspect of the enduser. This causes a decoupling between model recommendations and the user's actual decision patterns, which can lower trust and adoption. This study

investigates how AI can help fill this gap by integrating behavioral finance knowledge into financial advisory systems.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

This survey discusses representative studies on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in behavioral finance, sentiment analysis, and portfolio management. The chosen papers address:

1. The use of AI and behavioral economics to influence consumer financial health.
2. The detection of specific investor biases using machine learning.
3. The development of advanced deep reinforcement learning (DRL) frameworks for high-dimensional portfolio management.
4. The creation of a reinforcement learning framework that adapts to customizable stock pools without retraining
5. The application of sentiment analysis to predict market behavior.

1. Ben-David, Mintz, and Sade, Working Paper (2020)

AI and Behavioral Nudges for Overdraft Fee Reduction

Ben-David et al. implemented a randomized field study with a large personal financial management platform to examine mechanisms for lowering overdraft charges. They employed an AI algorithm to classify users as likely to overdraft their accounts and dispatched them reminder alerts with varying framings. The research revealed that sending a reminder was effective, but its impact was greatly increased if the message was simplified. In addition, a negatively phrased simple message ("Avoid Paying \$34.00 Fee") elicited more user activity and had a higher, longer-lasting effect on fee reductions than a positively phrased one ("Save \$34.00"). The impacts were largest with users who had medium to high yearly incomes.

2. Bhorge et al., IJIRT (2024)

Financial Sentiment Analysis using Transformer Models

Bhorge et al. surveyed recent advances in sentiment analysis for finance with an emphasis on sentiment extraction from

domains such as financial news and social media to forecast market behavior. The authors compared the performances of various sentiment classification models, including a classic Naive Bayes classifier with TF-IDF features, a standard BERT model, and FinBERT, an adaptation of BERT pre-trained on a huge dataset of financial documents. The outcomes indicated that the domain-specific FinBERT model clearly surpassed the overall BERT model and the classical Naive Bayes method in accuracy, reaching 85%

3. Jiang, Olmo, and Atwi, *Global Finance Journal* (2024)

Deep Reinforcement Learning for High Dimensional Portfolio Selection

Jiang et al. introduced a state-of-the-art model-free deep reinforcement learning (DRL) framework to build optimal portfolio strategies for intricate, high-dimensional markets such as the Dow Jones Industrial Average and S&P100. Their model integrates investor risk aversion and trading costs into the reward function and utilizes a Twin-Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (TD3) algorithm to manage the high dimensional state and action spaces. The proposed RTC-CNN-TD3 portfolio showed better performance than conventional approaches (Minimum Variance, Max-Sharpe) and competing DRL approaches (PPO, DDPG), with greater cumulative returns, Sharpe ratios, and Calmar ratios on out-of-sample testing.

4. Zhang et al., *WWW* (2024)

RL for Customizable Stock Pools using Maskable Representation

Zhang et al. tackled the challenge of using reinforcement learning for portfolio management when investors have adjustable stock pools (CSPs)—a situation where retraining an RL agent for every slight modification is costly computationally. They introduced Earn More, a model that trains an agent once on a world pool of stocks. The model employs a new mechanism for masking stocks outside an investor's target pool and learns useful representations in a self-supervised process of masking and reconstruction. This enables the agent to adapt dynamically to different CSPs without retraining and substantially outperforms 14 baselines on a variety of financial metrics

5. Gupta and Rao, *Journal of Informatics Education and Research* (2025)

Detecting Investor Bias with Supervised Machine Learning

Gupta and Rao examined how machine learning methods can detect and analyze investor behavior biases. With a data set of transaction records and sentiment analysis, they used random forest, support vector machine (SVM), and decision tree classifiers to identify patterns related to typical biases. Their random forest model had the best accuracy (87.4%),

pinning loss aversion as the most common bias (43% of profiles), followed by confirmation bias (27%) and overconfidence (18%). The research points out that ML offers a scalable structure to segment investors based on behavioral characteristics instead of demographics, making personalization of financial advice more possible.

Comparative Analysis

The literature surveyed illustrates a wide variety of AI applications in finance. These range from explicit behavioral treatments, as in applying Altimed reminders to avoid consumer overdrafts (Ben-David et al.), to passive detection of inherent psychological biases such as loss aversion from trading data (Gupta and Rao). Some of the other essential tasks are market forecasting based on sentiment analysis from social media and news (Bhorge et al.) and fully autonomous trading strategy development where Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) agents directly control portfolios to maximize returns (Jiang et al., Zhang et al.).

Data and Methodological Trends

The sources of data are as varied as the tasks, from large proprietary user transaction histories to public stock market information (e.g., S&P 500), investor histories, and textual data from financial news

Methodologically, some major trends are observed:

Supervised Learning models such as Random Forest and SVM are widely employed to handle classification tasks, for example, identifying behavioral biases of investors. In Natural Language Processing (NLP), there is a distinct trend towards domain-specialized transformer models such as FinBERT, which perform by far better than generalized models on finance text. For complicated, sequential tasks such as portfolio optimization, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) is the prevalent, state-of-the-art paradigm, with newer algorithms such as TD3 being preferred due to their stability in high-dimensional worlds

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

“There is a need for an AI-based investment system that integrates market data with investor behavioral biases to deliver explainable and adaptive recommendations.”

3.2 PROBLEM ELABORATION

The existing AI-based investment platforms primarily focus on financial metrics and trend analysis but largely ignore behavioral factors that influence real-world investment decisions. Cognitive biases such as overconfidence, loss aversion, and emotional trading significantly affect investor actions and decision quality. The proposed framework bridges this gap by combining behavioral profiling with

market analytics through real-time adaptive learning. It emphasizes explainable AI, enabling transparent and bias-aware investment suggestions that improve decision accuracy, risk assessment, and investor trust.

3.3 PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The intended model combines behavioral finance concepts with reinforcement learning and machine learning algorithms to develop an investment advisory system that is dynamic in nature. The architecture entails seven main layers: Continuous Learning Loop, Portfolio Management Dashboard, Explainability and Feedback Layer, AI Investment Engine, Market Data Aggregation Layer, Behavioral Profiling Module, and User Input Layer.

3.3.1 User Input Layer

Gathers investor information like financial objectives, investment time frame, and risk tolerance.

Records interaction patterns and emotional signals while using the platform.

3.3.2 Behavioral Profiling Module

Analyzes historical transactions and interaction history.

Identifies behavioral biases (overconfidence, loss aversion, impulsiveness, etc.).

Constructs an adaptive risk profile that evolves with new information.

3.3.3 Market Data Aggregation Layer

Combines real-time and past financial information.

Sources are stock prices, news sentiment, and macroeconomic data.

Utilizes APIs like Yahoo Finance and social media sentiment APIs.

3.3.4 AI Investment Engine

Utilizes machine learning and reinforcement learning techniques.

Optimizes portfolios and provides context sensitive, risk-adjusted recommendations.

3.3.5 Explainability and Feedback Layer

Uses Explainable AI (XAI) techniques (e.g., SHAP, attention).

Shows rationale for recommendations and collects user feedback for retraining.

3.3.6 Portfolio Management Dashboard

Offers individualized portfolio summaries, notifications, and behavioral analysis.

Allows users to track performance and modify preferences.

3.3.7 Continuous Learning Loop

Periodically updates models using fresh market and behavioral data.

Improves forecast accuracy and evolves with altering investor behavior.

Fig -1: Flowchart of the Proposed System

4. SURVEY OF TECHNICAL CONCEPTS

This section discusses the key technical elements of the proposed behavioral finance-inclined investment system, such as behavioral bias identification, reinforcement learning, explainable AI, and adaptive systems.

4.1 Behavioral Bias Detection

ML models scan transactional data—trade frequency, portfolio concentration, and realized gains/losses—to identify investor biases like:

- **Disposition Effect:** Tendency to hold losing assets for too long.
- **Loss Aversion:** Resistance to realize losses.
- **Overconfidence & Impulsiveness:** High-frequency trading and concentrated investments.

Adaptive behavioral profiles are created and refreshed with user activity.

4.2 Reinforcement Learning in Portfolio Management

RL facilitates dynamic decision-making by engaging with simulated trading conditions, trading off exploration and exploitation. Methods are:

- **Q-Learning:** Optimizes the selection of stocks.
- **Deep RL (DRL):** Facilitates dynamic risk management and asset allocation

These methods enable the system to adapt real-time to market volatility and risk limits.

4.3 Explainable AI in Finance

XAI enhances AI recommendation transparency and trust through:

- **Feature Importance:** SHAP, LIME.
- **Attention-Based Models:** Identify key inputs.
- **Counterfactual Explanations:** Display alternative outcomes and risks.

4.4 Adaptive Systems

Online learning and recurrent model updates enable the system to evolve with changing markets and investor behavior, making precise, timely, and individualized recommendations in the long run

5. CHALLENGES AND OPEN ISSUES

Merging AI with behavioral finance involves a number of technical as well as ethical issues that need to be resolved for real-world adoption

5.1 Data Privacy and Ethics

Financial and behavioral information is very sensitive. Regulation compliance like GDPR, along with safe anonymization and encryption, is mandatory.

5.2 Model Robustness

AI models need to be stable under turbulent market conditions, such as financial crises and geopolitical shocks, and subject to stress testing and robustness validation.

5.3 Bias Generalization

Overfitting to specific user behavior can restrict generalization. Models need to balance personalization with flexibility across different investor cohorts.

5.4 Explainability vs. Complexity

Deep-learning models are very accurate but not very explainable, whereas less complex models are very transparent but less accurate. A balance between accuracy and explainability is essential.

5.5 User Adoption and Trust

Trust from investors is extremely important. A human-in-the-loop system enables users to verify decisions made by AI and offer feedback, increasing transparency, accountability, and uptake

6. CONCLUSIONS

The suggested AI-based investment system well combines behavioral finance concepts with smart decision models. Through the integration of behavioral profiling, market analysis, and explainable AI, it gives adaptive and transparent investment suggestions. This strategy boosts investor confidence, minimizes bias, and enables data-driven financial planning. Future developments will center on adopting real investor datasets, enhancing privacy controls, and enhancing model interpretability without sacrificing accuracy.

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